

Pest resistance — insects

Development of a brown planthopper (BPH) biotype and change in varietal resistance in Mekong Delta

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In 1988 wet season, we collected three new BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal populations developed from BPH biotype 2 on rice variety OM80 at Omon district, northern Haugiang Province, and on IR64 at Chauthanh and Phutan districts, central and northeast Angiang Province, in the Mekong Delta. IR64 (or OM89) was introduced to farmers in 1983 and OM80 in 1984. Their BPH resistance was broken by a new BPH population in 4-5 yr.

We tested for biotype identification and screened varieties by the standard seedbox test. Test lines were sown in 20-cm-long rows at 30 seeds/row in 60- × 40- × 10-cm wood seedboxes filled 5 cm deep with fine soil, in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Seedlings were infested 7 d after seeding with second- to third-instar BPH nymphs at 5-8 nymphs/plant. Damage was scored when 95% of susceptible check TN1 had died.

Varieties with no resistance gene or with *Bph 1* gene were very susceptible or

Table 1. Reaction of differential check varieties to new BPH population.^a CLRRI, 1988 wet season.

Variety	Gene for BPH resistance	Reaction to BPH populations			
		Chauthanh (Angiang)	Phutan (Angiang)	Omon (Haugiang)	CLRRI (Biotype 2)
TN1	None	9	9	9	9
IR8	None	9	9	9	9
IR28	<i>Bph 1</i>	7	7	7	7
IR30	<i>Bph 1</i>	5	7	7	7
IR36	<i>bph 2</i>	7	5	3	1
IR38	<i>bph 2</i>	5	3	1	3
Ptb 33	digenic	1	3	1	1

^aAv of 3 replications, by the *Standard evaluation system for rice*

Table 2. Comparison of reaction of modern varieties to old and new BPH populations. CLRRI, 1988 wet season.

Variety	Year introduced	Reaction	
		Old population Omon, 1988	New population Angiang, 1989
MTL 61 (IR19728-9-3-2)	1986	1	5
MTL 58 (IR13240-108-2-2-3)	1986	3	7
OM87-1 (IR31802-48-2-2-2)	1987	1	5
OM86-9 (IR74) (IR32429-47-3-2-2)	1986	-	5
OM606-1-1-1-1 (IR42/Tran chau lun)	1989	3	5
OM87-9 (IR31868-64-2-3-3)	1987	3	5
OM576-18-1-1 (Hungary/IR42)	1988	3	5
OM296 (Than nong do/IR48)	1989	0	3
OM44-5 (OM90/OM80)	1889	0	3
NN4B (IR42)	1982	5	7
IR64 (IR18348-36-3-3)	1983	1	5
IR66 (IR32307-107-3-2-2)	1986	3	5
IR68 (IR28224-3-2-3-2)	1989	1	5
IR70 (IR28228-12-3-1)	1989	1	5
CR94-12 (resistant check)		0	5
IR36 (resistant check)		1	5
TN1 (susceptible check)		9	9

susceptible to all new BPH populations; varieties with *bph 2* were attacked by the BPH population in Angiang (damage rating 5-7) but were still resistant to the BPH population in Haugiang (Table 1). Ptb 33 with digenic resistance genes was resistant to all new BPH populations.

BPH virulence appears to have shifted higher than that of BPH biotype 2 in Angiang.

Most varieties resistant to BPH biotype 2 were moderately susceptible to the new biotype (Angiang population) (Table 2). ■

Stress tolerance — drought

Genetic variability in midday leaf water potential (LWP) of irrigated rice

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In rice, midday LWP falls, even in irrigated rice, because of a lag between water absorption by roots and transpira-

tion through the leaves. This indicates that midday LWP may be a criterion to use in selecting for drought resistance.

We grew six advanced upland breeding lines and two varieties under irrigated field conditions in 1988 dry season to evaluate genetic variability in midday LWP.

Experimental 5- × 5-m plots were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. At maximum tillering, the LWP of 10

penultimate, fully expanded leaves of each variety in each replication were measured at 1200-1300 h under clear skies, using standard pressure chamber technique.

Differences among varieties were significant (see table). The highest LWP was in BR4290-3-1-10, the lowest in BR4290-3-3-5. The differential LWP observed suggests that LWP may be used as a drought resistance selection criterion. ■